

ENSURING CONTINUITY IN EDUCATION AND TRAINING BASED ON A COGNITIVE APPROACH: TEACHING METHODS, INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES, AND PERSPECTIVES ON DEEP LANGUAGE ACQUISITION. AN OVERVIEW OF COGNITIVE APPROACH IN LANGUAGE LEARNING.

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ABSTRACT

This scientific article describes cognitive approach's several conceptions as well as, Cognitive Theory in Language Learning, Cognitive Method in Language Learning, Cognitive Technique in Language Learning, The Strength of Cognitive Approach in Language Learning and The Limitation of Cognitive Approach in Language Learning.

Keywords: cognitive theory, cognitive activities, cognitive tools, the limitation of cognitive approach, cognitive development.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В этой научной статье описываются несколько концепций когнитивного подхода, а также «Когнитивная теория в изучении языка», «Когнитивный метод в изучении языка», «Когнитивная техника в изучении языка», «Сила когнитивного подхода в изучении языка» и «Ограничение когнитивного подхода в изучении языка».

Ключевые слова: когнитивная теория, познавательная деятельность, познавательные средства, ограничения когнитивного подхода, когнитивное развитие.

Introduction. Cognitivism as a theory of learning studies about the process occurs inside the learner's mind has the own history about how it happens or the development of it. The development of cognitivism theory is famous with the term "cognitive revolution". According to asiaeuniversity the cognitive revolution is the name for an intellectual movement in the 1950s that began with what are known collectively as the cognitive sciences. It began in the modern context of greater interdisciplinary communication and research. Although cognitive psychology

emerged in the late 1950s and began to take over as the dominant theory of learning. It wasn't until the late 1970s that cognitive science began to have its influence on instructional design (Mergel,1998). From the assumptions of the two experts, I can infer that the development of cognitivism happened in the 1950s as the dominant theory of learning. Unfortunately, the impact of it in the language learning occurred in 1970s. One of the real impacts is the influence on instructional design. In this case, the development of cognitive theory in psychology is as the response of behaviorism. As we know that, behaviorism is the theory of language learning which emphasize in observable behavior. The answer why cognitivism theory appears as the response of behaviorism theory was because the behaviorist psychologist tried to avoid the use of mental process in our mind. They tried to erase the cognitivism theory. In other words, they just would like to explain something which is observable, not the unobservable one (cognitivism).

FACTORS INFLUENCED THE DEVELOPMENT OF COGNITIVISM

After we know the history of cognitivism, it is important for us to know the factors influenced the development of it. According to Jordan, Carlite & Stack (2008: 36-37) there are four factors influenced it. They are the development of experimental psychology, the move from an interest in external behaviors to internal brain process, the inadequacy of computer and an interest in artificial intelligence.

DEFINITION OF COGNITIVISM

According to Mergel (1998) cognitivism is a cognitivist theory that based on thought process behind the behavior. It means that the theory occurs inside the learners mind consciously. Moreover, it focuses on how people think, how people understand, and how people know (asiaeuniversity, 2012:107).How people think is the theory stresses in how our ways of thinking will impact to the behavior. How people understand is the theory shows the people's understanding related to outside world. How people know is the theory shows how the people know phenomenon outside the world. Of course, it derives from the process that happens in human mind.

PRINCIPLES OF COGNITIVISM

Cognitivism involves the study of mental processes such as sensation, perception, attention, encoding, and memory that behaviorists were reluctant to study because cognition occurs inside the "black box" of the brain (Jordan, Carlite & Stack, 2008:36). In this case, sensation perception, attention, encoding, and memory are the principle of cognitivism. The followings are the explanation of them.

Methodology. Cognitive is a learning theory that emphasized in the process which happens inside the learners. In this case, there are three important types of cognitive theories. They are Piaget's cognitive development theory, Vygotsky's socio cultural cognitive theory and the information processing approach.

Piaget's Cognitive Development (1896-1980)

Piaget is the famous psychologist from Swiss who describes cognitive theory in the cognitive developmental theory. According to Hebb (2003: 3) Piaget's theory states the children actively construct their understanding of the world and go through stages of cognitive development. It means that Piaget described cognitivism in the stage development of children when they are ready to construct the meaning of things through their own understanding which starts from the simple to complex thing. Knowledge and thinking skills provide the substance and tools for cognitive problem solving (Bandura, 1989:9). There are two processes underlie in cognitive construction. They are organization and adaptation. Organization is important in order the children construct the meaning of thing which make sense to them by organizing our experience. For example we specify the less and important ideas then we connect them. While adaptation is useful when we add the new information in our thinking system because there is important additional information. In this case, adaptation is differentiated into two ways.

Cognitive Theory in Language Learning

Cognitive theory in language learning is in accordance with two modern theories : cognitive linguistics theory and cognitive psychology theory. Cognitive linguistics theory describes how language interacts with cognition, how language forms our thoughts and the evolution of language parallel with the change in the common mindset across time. (Robinson& Peter, 2008) It was first proposed by Gerge Lakoff in 1987 in "Women, Fire, and Dangerous Thing." Later, other scholars began developing their own approach to language description and linguistic theory. (Wallace Chafe, 1987; Charles Fillmore 2006) The most influential view shared by all the linguists is meaning should be a primary focus of study.

Cognitive Method in Language Learning

Method refers to more specific way of learning than approach. From the view of cognitive method, learning strategy (students) and teaching method (teacher) should be centered around student' mental process rather than the external behavior and it is teachers' role in guiding individual to focus on their internal learning process and learning style should be noted. Cognitive strategies include repetition, organizing new language, summarizing meaning, guessing meaning from context, using imagery

for memorization, all of these strategies involve delivering manipulation of language to improve learning. Teaching method encompasses content enhancement, content evaluation, determination of necessary approaches and routines and instructional supports. (Bulgren & Scalon,1997) Content-based method and student-led seminar are two favored ways in cognitive language learning class. Cognitive Technique in Language Learning

Cognitive Activities

Technique reflects activities or tools used by teachers. In cognitive language learning, activities used should focus on the effects in developing students' thinking ability and problem-solving ability. The goal is to get them thinking and applying problem-solving strategies without the use of preparation or steps that lead to an answer. Cognitive activities includes making mind maps, visualization, association, mnemonics, using clues in reading comprehension, underlining key words, scanning, self-testing and monitoring and etc.

Cognitive Tools: Learning with Technology

Cognitive tools mean learning with technology. Jonassen (1994) stated that technologies as tools can provide learners with meaningful thinking, which correlates closely with cognitive view. There are five classes of cognitive tools suggested by Jonassen and Carr (2000): semantic organization tools, dynamic modeling tools, visualization tools, knowledge construction tools and socially shared cognitive tools. The five tools cover comprehensible aspects of language learning including semantics, grammar, social linguistics and etc, providing instructions for teachers' chose of technology tools in developing students' cognitive ability. Common cognitive tools are concept maps, knowledge forum, blogs and just to name a few.

The Strength of Cognitive Approach in Language Learning

Unlike the behavioral approach, cognitive approach aims to discover what might be the better way for the acquisition of language in our mind. It highlights how mental process greatly influences behavior and the disparity of learning effects. This has positive significance for those who want to use the cognition to change their learning behavior for the better. Cognitive approach is, furthermore, a flexible theory which can be easily combined with other theories to make more positive results. For example, cognitive- behaviour therapy is a compound therapy, striving to create more favorable behavior by changing cognition. It is proved to be greatly useful in language learning. The Limitation of Cognitive Approach in Language Learning The first limitation of cognitive approach in language learning lies in its ignorance of emotional variables. For example, most cognitive tools such as database processor

emphasize on the logical aspects of cognitive approach instead of emotional aspects. Language, as known to all, is more than merely communication tools and correlates closely with emotion, culture and society. The ignorance of emotional variables and subjective aspects, undoubtedly, have a negative impact on learners' use of language in reality. The second limitation of cognitive approach in language learning focuses on whether what we view the working procedure of our mind is true. Cognitive approach often relies on comparisons with how human mind might work. The method and tools we design and use is mainly based on the assumptions without enough evidence and the technology even the newest is unable to compare with the complex operating process of our mind. It is, therefore, difficult to confirm the effectiveness of cognitive approach.

Results. Strength and weaknesses

Cognitivism is a theory of learning studies about the process occurs inside the learner's. So, as a teacher who wants to apply the cognitivism in his or her teaching learning process, he or she must consider the strength and weaknesses of it when it applies in classroom. The weakness of cognitivism is the learners learn the way to finish the task, but it is not a good way. The strength is the students are trained to do the task in the same way to produce the students who have consistency behavior (Schuman, 1996 in Mergel, 1998).

Discussion

The educational implication of cognitive theories

According to Suharno (2010:60) the cognitive view takes the learner to be an active processor of information. It means that the cognitive theory tries to create the people to be active to think. The implication of cognitive theories in educational field is try to produce the students to find the problem solving. do discovery learning, cognitive strategies, and project based learning.

Discovery learning is one of the applications of cognitivism. According to O'Donnell (1997) "Discovery Learning is an instructional method in which the students are free to work in learning environment with little or no guidance". This assumption from O'Donnell is also supported by Ryan & Muray (2009) who assume that discovery learning is problem based learning with minimal guidance". It means that through discovery learning the teacher gives opportunity to students to explore their selves by learning through the environment with little guidance from the teacher. There are some structures that must be paid attention in applying discovery

learning. They are readiness to learn, intuitive and analytical thinking, motivates for learning. These structures must be moved from basic to advanced step.³²

Conclusion.

Cognitive theory is learning theory of psychology that attempts to explain human behavior by understanding the thought process. It is emphasized in the conscious thought. The theory was born in the 1950s. There are four factors influenced the development of it. They are experimental psychology, the shift from behaviorism to cognition, language acquisition and computer artificial intelligence. In this case, cognitivism is divided into three important cognitive theories emphasize their conscious thoughts. They are Piaget's cognitive development theory, Vygotsky's socio cultural cognitive theory, and the information processing approach. All of the types of cognitive theory stress on the important of process that is happening inside the human's mind. The application of cognitive theory can be applied through problem based learning, discovery learning, cognitive strategies, and project based learning. Overall the goal of its application is to create the students to be active in teaching learning process.

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³² Robinson & Peter, 2008, Wallace Chafe, 1987; Charles Fillmore 2006, Bulgren & Scalon, 1997, Lajoie (1993, p.261), Jordan, Carlite & Stack, 2008:36.

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